

IRISCC

D9.2

First report with statistics on use of the RI services including assessment reports from IAP

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Abstract

Key words

Virtual Access, Climate Risk Services, Research Infrastructures, Catalogue of Services.

This deliverable presents the first report following the integration of the initial release (R1) Virtual Access (VA) services into the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS). These services, contributed by participating European Research Infrastructures (RIs), provide remote access to data, tools, and resources supporting climate change risk assessment and response. They cover key domains including atmospheric observations, climate modelling, and aerosol analysis, and offer open-access platforms for both real-time and historical datasets.

The report presents usage tracking for the ten R1 services under Task 9.2. It also includes an assessment conducted by the International Assessment Panel (IAP), highlighting service performance and overall scientific value.

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Terminology / Acronyms

The present table lists the most relevant acronyms used throughout this document. Well-known abbreviations and proper names of Research Infrastructures and institutions have been omitted.

Term/Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface. A set of protocols that allow software applications to communicate and exchange data.
ATMO-ACCESS	An EU-funded project supporting sustainable access to atmospheric research facilities and infrastructures.
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project. International framework for coordinating and comparing climate model experiments across modeling centers worldwide
CoS	Catalogue of Services. The online platform (https://www.iriscc.eu/catalogue-of-services) lists all services—virtual, remote, and physical—offered through IRISCC.
EARLINET	European Aerosol Research Lidar Network. Pan-European network of lidar stations providing aerosol optical property profiles.
EBAS	Database hosted at NILU providing harmonised atmospheric composition measurements from monitoring networks including ACTRIS.
ECV	Essential Climate Variable. Key atmospheric, oceanic, and terrestrial parameters essential for understanding climate variability and change.
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation. Distributed infrastructure for climate model data access and sharing.
EWA	Early Warning for Aviation. Alert service for volcanic ash and desert dust concentration levels relevant to aviation safety.
IFS	Integrated Forecasting System. Meteorological analysis model operated by ECMWF, used as input for atmospheric transport modelling.
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. UN body responsible for assessing the science related to climate change.
IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks. An EU-funded project delivering scientific services and knowledge tools to support research and policy for climate resilience in Europe.

NRT / RRT	Near-Real-Time / Real-Real-Time – Timeliness indicators for data delivery and visualization services.
QC	Quality Control. Set of procedures ensuring the accuracy and reliability of scientific data.
RI	Research Infrastructure. Facilities, resources and services used by the science community to conduct research and foster innovation.
STILT	Stochastic Time-Inverted Lagrangian Transport. Atmospheric transport model used to compute source-receptor relationships for greenhouse gas measurements.
VA	Virtual access means free access to Users provided through communication networks; the available services or resources can be simultaneously used by an unlimited number of Users and the Users are not selected. Virtual access typically concerns access to data and digital tools.
WP	Work Package. Defined subtask within a project to achieve a specific goal or result.

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the first report following the integration of the initial release (R1) Virtual Access (VA) services into the IRISCC Catalogue of Services (CoS). These services, contributed by participating European Research Infrastructures (RIs), make data, tools, and resources available through digital services supporting climate change risk assessment and response. They cover key domains including atmospheric observations, climate modelling, and aerosol analysis, and offer open-access platforms for both real-time and historical datasets. A full description of the VA services is provided in Deliverable [D9.1 Report defining and describing R1 services](#).

The report presents usage tracking for the ten R1 services under Task 9.2 to support performance evaluation. It also includes an assessment conducted by the International Assessment Panel (IAP), highlighting service performance and overall scientific value. Usage tracking is implemented through the VA management system developed in WP8 and builds on best practices from previous projects.

1. Introduction

Work Package 9 (WP9) of the IRISCC project, titled "VA01 – Virtual Access Provision for Climate Change Risk Services", aims to provide seamless online access to digital services crucial for understanding, mitigating, and adapting to climate change risks. VA services span a wide range of types – datasets, analysis tools, modelling services, and scientific resources – with significantly different levels of maturity, scope, and user interaction models.

The primary objective of WP9 is to coordinate and implement access to services developed and provided by participating Research Infrastructures (RIs). These services are intended to support a broad user community, ranging from researchers and policymakers to practitioners and the public, in accessing high-quality data and analytical tools relevant to climate-related risks.

Task 9.2 builds on the work conducted in Task 9.1, which focused on collecting the technical and operational information required to onboard services into the [IRISCC Catalogue of Services \(CoS\)](#) and the VA management system developed in WP8 (see [D8.2 Optimised IRISCC VA Management System](#), r1 in Section 6). Based on this foundation, Task 9.2 is responsible for the operational deployment and provision of the initial release (R1) services to users through the VA management system. The task also includes user support and the monitoring of service usage.

Usage tracking plays a key role in assessing how the VA services are accessed and used, supporting both performance evaluation and continuous improvement of service provision. In this context, the VA management system developed in WP8 serves as the central tool for collecting usage data.

An International Assessment Panel (IAP), consisting of a pool of external experts has been established by WP8. From this pool, a subset of members is selected to review each VA service (2 reviewers by service, each reviewer in charge of 2 services). The IAP has been asked for periodic assessment reports every 18 months. So far, the IAP has been asked to review the first 12 months of R1 VA services.

This deliverable presents an overview of the R1 services available through the IRISCC Catalogue of Services, followed by an analysis of their usage and a summary of the assessment provided by the IAP.

All services are provided under open access, although some may require a registration or access request prior to use.

2. List of R1 services

Table 1 summarizes the R1 services as defined in the IRISCC Grant Agreement, providing an overview of their associated installations, CoS entries, and contact points for further information.

Table 1. Overview of VA services for R1.

Overview of VA services promised for 1 st Release				
#	Installation		Service name	Catalogue of Services (CoS)
01	IAGOS-DC_CNRS	<u>Installation 344</u>	Climatologies & anomalies of ECVs	<u>Service 597</u>
02	IAGOS-DC_KIT		Anomalies of volatile organic compounds	<u>Service 804</u>
03	IS-ENES DKRZ	<u>Installation 370</u>	Climate4Impact	<u>Service 806</u>
04	IS-ENES KNMI		Climate Model Data Access Portal	<u>Service 802</u>
05	ECA&D KNMI	<u>Installation 377</u>	European Climate Assessment & Dataset	<u>Service 848</u> <u>Service 849</u>
06	ACTRIS-DC at NILU	<u>Installation 337</u>	RRT/NRT Quick Looks (In-Situ)	<u>Service 596</u>
07			Aerosol Remote Sensing Quicklook Interface	<u>Service 601</u>
08	ACTRIS-DC at CNRS		ECV Climatologies	<u>Service 803</u>
09	ACTRIS-DC at FMI		Early warning for aviation from aerosol lidar ground-based observations	<u>Service 862</u>
10	ICOS Carbon Portal at ULUND	Onboarding in progress	ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service	Onboarding in progress

3. Usage tracking

As outlined in the introduction, the VA services of RI encompass a wide range of types, with varying levels of maturity and scope. While all services are fully operational, some are expected to be further improved and consolidated over time. Consequently, usage tracking approaches differ across services to reflect their specific characteristics. As all VA services are provided under open access, the data collected primarily consist of aggregated quantitative metrics rather than identifiable user information.

In line with recommendations from the ATMO-ACCESS project, service providers have been encouraged to implement lightweight and service-appropriate tracking methods. These include:

- the number of daily visits (common to all services);
- additional service-specific metrics, such as number of downloads, volume of data downloaded, and number of requests (with a clear definition of what constitutes a request).

These metrics have been harmonised to enable consistent interpretation across services, while remaining flexible enough to reflect the nature of each service.

The VA management system developed in WP8 serves as the central platform for collecting usage data, supported by a RESTful API that enables automated reporting by service providers. While not all providers have been able to fully implement automated reporting, they have supplied their usage data in the required format, ensuring consistency with the API specifications. However, in some cases, providers were not able to set up metric aggregation in time, resulting in either missing data for the reporting period or a limited set of available metrics.

It should be noted that, while these usage indicators provide valuable insights into service uptake and performance, they remain limited in their ability to fully capture user engagement, impact, or quality of use. Differences in tracking implementations and service maturity should therefore be considered when interpreting the results.

The following Sections (Sections 3.1–3.10) present a service-by-service overview, including a brief reminder of each service's specifications followed by the corresponding usage statistics.

Table 2 provides an aggregated overview of the reported usage metrics across all VA services for the reporting period. The accompanying figures (Figures 1–8) illustrate the distribution and evolution of the main usage indicators across services.

Table 2. Overview of total metrics of all VA services

Statistic	Total
Visits	9 437
Downloads	1 352 051 967
Download size (TB)	37 460
Requests	420 669

Figure 1. Total Visits by month — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 2. Total Visits by country — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 3. Total Downloads by month — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 4. Total Downloads by country — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 5. Total Download size (MB) by month — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 6. Total Download size (MB) by country — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 7. Total Requests by month — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 8. Total Requests by country — all services, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.1 IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere

3.1.1 Description

Table 3 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 3: Description of service IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere

Service information	
Service name	IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere
Service ID	597
Installation	IAGOS-DC_CNRS
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/597
Direct link	https://services.iagos-data.fr/iriscc/anomalies
Contact	damien.boulangier@cnrs.fr
Description	
<p>The IAGOS Anomalies viewer is an interactive web interface that provides visualisation of anomalies in IAGOS long time series of observations (ozone, carbon monoxide, water vapour). It includes several features:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • selection of variables • selection of proposed or custom vertical layers • selection of airports • selection of display mode and aggregation methods • selection and visualisation of specific vertical profiles 	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>The scientific objectives of the service is to provide diagnostics and statistics for a better understanding of the long time series, offering the possibility of the creation of a "tailored data set for Earth System Models evaluation/improvement", and giving the broader context of dedicated campaigns or experiments.</p>	
Support to users	
<p>User guide: https://iagos.aeris-data.fr/iriscc-anomalies-viewer-user-guide/</p>	
Target user community	
<p>The target user community is the international scientific community from Academia as well as operational services like Meteorological services and Copernicus services</p>	

3.1.2 Number of visits

Figures 9 and 10 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 9. IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere — Visits by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 10. IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere — Visits by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.1.3 Other metrics

Figures 11 and 12 present the usage metrics of the service over the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31. A request corresponds to the number of anomalies visualised by a user. The figures illustrate both the temporal evolution of these requests and their geographical distribution by country.

IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere — Metrics by month

Figure 11. IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere — Metrics by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 12. IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere — requests by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.2 IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of VOCs

3.2.1 Description

Table 4 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 4. Description of service IAGOS anomalies of volatile organic compounds in the troposphere

Service information	
Service name	IAGOS anomalies of volatile organic compounds in the troposphere
Service ID	804
Installation	IAGOS-DC_KIT
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/804
Direct link	https://iagos-caribic.atmohub.kit.edu/iriscc/
Contact	andreas.zahn@kit.edu
Description	
<p>This service is an interactive web interface that identifies flight paths that are affected by biomass burning plumes and provides the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • selection of flight • identification of flight section that have been affected by biomass burning plumes (detected using acetonitrile as an unambiguous tracer for biomass burning) • visualization of the cross-section of up to 2 variables along the flight path (out of >30 variables) • additional display of back trajectories to indicate origin 	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>This service identifies IAGOS-CARIBIC flight paths which have been affected by biomass burning plumes, shows the relevant air mass back trajectories for illustrating their origin and displays cross-section of many other trace species, inter alia, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), aerosol, ozone, CO and many others.</p> <p>The service helps to show which regions of the (mainly upper) troposphere are affected by biomass burning plumes, at which times in the year and what the impact on (many) other trace species is.</p>	
Target user community	
<p>The target user community is the international scientific community from Academia as well as operational services like Meteorological services and Copernicus services</p>	

3.2.2 Number of visits

No statistics are available for the period covered by this report. Statistical monitoring will be implemented for the next reporting period.

3.3 IS-ENES Climate4Impact

3.3.1 Description

Table 5 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 5. Description of service CLIMATE4IMPACT portal.

Service information	
Service name	CLIMATE4IMPACT portal
Service ID	806
Installation	IS-ENES at DKRZ and KNMI
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/806
Direct link	https://www.climate4impact.eu/
Contact	alessandro.spinuso@knmi.nl
Description	
<p>Climate4Impact (C4I) is a web platform developed within the IS-ENES European climate modelling infrastructure that provides easy access to major climate model datasets, such as CMIP, through the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF). Operated by KNMI, it enables researchers and climate service providers to discover and explore climate projections without handling complex data infrastructures locally.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>The scientific objectives of Climate4Impact (C4I) are centred on making climate model data easier to find and use for science, impacts research, and climate services. In practical terms, its main scientific objectives are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhance the use of climate research data • Bridge climate model outputs and impact applications • Support reproducible climate analytics through integrated processing services, Jupyter, workflows, and Python-based tools, • Provide scientifically guided use cases and best practices 	
Support to users	
<p>User Manuals and Guidance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portal: https://www.climate4impact.eu/c4i-frontend/helpC4I • Analysis Workspaces: https://www.climate4impact.eu/c4i-frontend/helpSwirrl • Scientific Notebooks: https://gitlab.com/is-enes-cdi-c4i/notebooks • Feedback form: <p>User feedback form: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScZoy7tbmb4rauvgHWRqhKaj4RpX6GGqJMCuLq-sf5sfO4Ozw/viewform</p>	

Target user community

The target user community of Climate4Impact (C4I) is centred on people who need climate model data for research, impacts analysis, and practical decision support. The main users include climate impact modellers, adaptation consultants, climate service providers, and researchers working with global and regional (coming-up) climate projections.

3.3.2 Number of visits

Figures 13 and 14 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 13. CLIMATE4IMPACT portal — Visits by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 14. CLIMATE4IMPACT portal — Visits by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.3.3 Other metrics

Figures 15 and 16 present the usage metrics of the service over the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31. A request corresponds to the number of build data requests by a user. The figures illustrate both the temporal evolution of these requests and their geographical

distribution by country.
CLIMATE4IMPACT portal — Metrics by month

Figure 15. CLIMATE4IMPACT portal — Metrics by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 16. CLIMATE4IMPACT portal — requests by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.4 IS-ENES Climate Model Data Access Portal

3.4.1 Description

Table 6 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 6. Description of service Climate Model Data Portal

Service information	
Service name	Climate Model Data Portal
Service ID	802
Installation	IS-ENES at DKRZ and KNMI
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/802
Direct link	https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/
Contact	kindermann@dkrz.de khan@dkrz.de
Description	
<p>The ESGF data portal hosted at DKRZ provides access to climate model data collections hosted as part of the IS-ENES infrastructure. It enables researchers to search data based on standardized metadata and download data based on different data transfer protocols. A primary data collection offered is CMIP6 climate model data generated as input for the latest IPCC climate report. The data portal is part of the global ESGF infrastructure which is currently being replaced by new components. Thus this data portal will be replaced during summer 2026. Additionally a data access service is integrated into the D4Science RI supporting the pre-processing of data as part of a data download activity.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>A major objective is to provide easy and transparent access to climate model data generated by modelling centres around the world as part of internationally coordinated climate model intercomparison projects (CMIPs). This data is of high importance for the climate modelling community as well as downstream communities as well as interdisciplinary climate research.</p>	
Support to users	
<p>The portal provides links to tutorials and FAQs. Extensive user support material is accessible at https://esgf.github.io/esgf-user-support/. A support team can be reached via esgf-user@llnl.gov.</p>	

Target user community

Multiple communities are targeted: 1) Climate modelling research community 2) downstream climate research communities, e.g. climate impact research 3) interdisciplinary climate research

3.4.2 Number of visits

Figures 17 and 18 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 17. Climate Model Data Portal — Visits by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 18. Climate Model Data Portal — Visits by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.4.3 Other metrics

Figures 19–21 present the usage statistics of the service over the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of user requests, the geographical distribution of downloads by country, and the associated download volumes expressed in MB.

Figure 19. Climate Model Data Portal — Metrics by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 20. Climate Model Data Portal — downloads by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 21. Climate Model Data Portal — downloads_size (MB) by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.5 European Climate Assessment & Dataset

3.5.1 Description

Table 7 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 7: Description of service European Climate Assessment & Dataset.

Service information	
Service name	European Climate Assessment & Dataset
Service ID	848 & 849
Installation	ECA&D KNMI
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/848
Direct link	https://www.ecad.eu/dailydata/IRISCC.php
Contact	karlijn.zaanen@knmi.nl eca@knmi.nl
Description	
<p>The European Climate Assessment & Dataset is a data portal and climate monitoring tool specific for Europe. It holds daily values of the atmospheric Essential Climate Variables and currently receives data from 89 participants for 65 countries and the ECA dataset contains data for 25817 meteorological stations throughout Europe and the Mediterranean.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>For service 848, the scientific objective of the current data entry is to get a better understanding of soil moisture across Europe. Existing observed records are usually of a few years in length which is too short for trend analysis and to put developing droughts into a historic perspective. The current dataset aims to relieve this issue by providing long records of soil moisture based on a state-of-the-art soil moisture model and observed meteorological input records which are decades long.</p> <p>For service 849, the scientific objective of the current data entry is to get a better understanding of snow depth in Central Europe and its variation in time and space.</p>	
Support to users	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Daily data dictionary and meta data dictionary: https://www.ecad.eu/dailydata/datadictionary.php Climate Indices dictionary: https://www.ecad.eu/indicesextremes/indicesdictionary.php User support: eca@knmi.nl 	

Target user community

The target community for ECA&D are (climate) scientists and the National Meteorological Services in Europe. ECA&D is the backbone of the Climate Data node of the World Meteorological Organisation's Regional Climate Centre for Europe. In that capacity, it is also a DCPC (Data Collecting and Producing Centre) which targets National Meteorological Services.

The dataset 848 for soil moisture is specifically aimed for hydrologists and the regional climate modelling community as it provides validation data for their models.

The dataset 849 is specifically aimed for climate scientists interested in monitoring variations in snow pack over Central Europe.

3.5.2 Number of visits

Figures 22 and 23 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2026-03-19 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 22. European Climate Assessment & Dataset — Visits over time, 2026-03-19 – 2026-03-31.

Figure 23. European Climate Assessment & Dataset — Visits by country, 2026-03-19 – 2026-03-31.

3.6 ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol In-situ)

3.6.1 Description

Table 8 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 8. Description of service RRT/NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements.

Service information	
Service name	RRT/NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements
Service ID	596
Installation	ACTRIS-DC at NILU
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/596
Direct link	https://ebas-nrt.nilu.no/
Contact	lemu@nilu.no
Description	
<p>The NILU Near Real-Time (NRT) service provides rapid access to preliminary atmospheric composition data from the EBAS database and the ACTRIS research infrastructure. It delivers harmonised data streams through web-based interfaces (https://ebas-nrt.nilu.no) and interoperable services (e.g. THREDDS: https://thredds.nilu.no/thredds/catalog/actris_nrt/catalog.html). The service includes near real-time data on aerosol particles, VOCs, NO_x, and Black Carbon (BC), together with time series visualisation tools supporting rapid identification of pollution episodes and atmospheric events.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>The service supports near real-time analysis of atmospheric composition and processes, including air pollution episodes, long-range transport, and extreme events. Time series visualisation enables rapid detection of atmospheric incidents and climate-relevant extremes. Observations of key variables such as Black Carbon (BC), a short-lived climate forcer, support source apportionment, air quality assessment, and evaluation of mitigation measures, as well as model evaluation and data assimilation.</p>	
Support to users	
<p>Users are supported through open access portals, machine-to-machine services, and standardised EBAS NetCDF data formats ensuring interoperability and reuse (documentation: https://ebas.pages.nilu.no/ebas-io/fileformat_netcdf/index.html). Practical usage examples are available via the ACTRIS Virtual Research Environment (VRE: https://data.actris.eu/vre). User support is also provided through the EBAS helpdesk (ebas@nilu.no).</p>	

Target user community

The service targets atmospheric researchers, air quality and climate modellers, and environmental agencies requiring timely observational data. It also supports operational services, policy-related applications, and users within European research infrastructures and projects such as ACTRIS and IRISCC.

3.6.2 Number of visits

Figure 24 provides an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visit.

Figure 24. RRT/NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements — Visits by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.6.3 Other metrics

Figure 25 presents the usage statistics of the service over the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of the number of downloads.

RRT/NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements — Metrics by month

Figure 25. RRT/NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements — Metrics by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-31.

3.7 ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol remote sensing)

3.7.1 Description

Table 9 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 9. Description of service Aerosol Remote Sensing Quicklook Interface.

Service information	
Service name	Aerosol Remote Sensing Quicklook Interface
Service ID	601
Installation	ACTRIS-DC at CNR
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/601
Direct link	https://quicklooks.earlinet.org/
Contact	services@actris-ares.eu
Description	
<p>A Quicklook interface providing harmonized and selectable visualization of pre-processed LiDAR data by the ACTRIS ARES Data Centre Unit for ACTRIS and EARLINET stations. Two different quicklook types are supported: attenuated backscatter quicklooks and volume linear depolarization ratio quicklooks. Additionally, a cloud mask is also available for each measurement. All the quicklooks are generated in Portable Network Graphics (PNG) format.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>The Quicklook interface enables researchers to easily access and explore LiDAR measurements, supporting the interpretation and understanding of atmospheric aerosol layering and variability. The volume depolarization and the attenuated backscatter wavelength dependence can provide a direct insight of aerosol optical properties and asphericity. Quicklook interface mainly consists of a calendar explorable by station and by date. By default, it displays the most recent month with measurements: days with available acquired (and submitted) data are shown.</p> <p>For user convenience, data collected at other stations for the same data/time slot selected by the user are also shown.</p>	
Support to users	
Ready-to-use web interface, support by email: services@actris-ares.eu	
Target user community	
Atmospheric research community and users within research infrastructures	

3.7.2 Number of visits

Figures 26 and 27 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2025-07-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 26. Aerosol Remote Sensing Quicklook Interface — Visits by month, 2025-07-15 – 2026-03-23.

Figure 27: Aerosol Remote Sensing Quicklook Interface — Visits by country, 2025-07-15 – 2026-03-23.

3.8 ACTRIS ECV Climatologies

3.8.1 Description

Table 10 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 10. Description of service Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations.

Service information	
Service name	Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations
Service ID	803
Installation	ACTRIS-DC at CNR
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/803
Direct link	https://earlinet.eu/level-3-data/
Contact	services@actris-ares.eu
Description	
<p>Climatologies of aerosol optical properties profiles, including aerosol extinction profiles, are provided by the ACTRIS ARES data centre unit for ACTRIS and EARLINET stations with sufficient data coverage to produce statistically representative products.</p> <p>The climatological products are Level 3 data obtained from the fully quality controlled (Level 2) data for providing useful aggregated information to the users. The Level 3 data are centrally processed by ACTRIS ARES. This allows the harmonization and reproducibility of the products. The detailed documentation and the data products can be found at the Level 3 data webpage.</p> <p>The last climatological dataset covers the 2000–2019 period and includes 33 stations over Europe and beyond.</p> <p>Visualization tools for users will be made available through this service. Based on climatological averages, a system for anomalies identification will be implemented.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>The Level 3 standard products contain climatological datasets obtained as aggregated products from the fully quality controlled (QC) aerosol optical products (i.e. Level 2 products). In order to avoid biases due to measurements made on purpose specifically for capturing special events, it is considered only a subset of data corresponding to regular schedule and measurements done for satellite validation purposes.</p> <p>Data are organized for stations in order to allow future updates of the climatological products even at station level. For each station, three types of data are released: profile values, integrated quantities, layer statistics. For each type of data, four different</p>	

temporal aggregations are provided: seasonal, annual, normal seasonal, normal monthly.

DOIs assigned to individual station datasets as well as to the climatological dataset collection for all stations:

https://doi.org/10.57837/cnr-ima/ares/actris-earlinet/level3/climatological/2000_2019/all

The identification of anomalies is relevant for the research community highlighting interesting case studies, but it is also of interest for stakeholders. The understanding of causes of observed analysis is key for a better definition of climate change and air quality policies.

Support to users

Ready-to-use web interface, support by email: services@actris-ares.eu

<https://earlinet.eu/level-3-data/>

Target user community

Atmospheric research community, users within research infrastructures and stakeholders

3.8.2 Number of visits

Figures 28 and 29 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2025-12-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 28. Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — Visits by month, 2025-12-02 – 2026-03-31.

Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — Visits by country

Figure 29. Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — Visits by country, 2025-12-02 – 2026-03-31.

3.8.3 Other metrics

Figures 30–32 present the usage statistics of the service over the period 2026-01-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of the downloads, the geographical distribution of downloads by country, and the associated download volumes expressed in MB.

Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — Metrics by month

Figure 30. Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — Metrics by month, 2025-12-02 – 2026-03-31.

Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — downloads by country

Figure 31. Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — downloads by country, 2025-12-02 – 2026-03-31.

Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — downloads_size (MB) by country

Figure 32. Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — downloads_size (MB) by country, 2025-12-02 – 2026-03-31.

3.9 ACTRIS Volcanic Ash Alerts

3.9.1 Description

Table 11 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 11. Description of service Early warning for aviation from aerosol lidar ground-based observations.

Service information	
Service name	Early warning for aviation from aerosol lidar ground-based observations
Service ID	862
Installation	ACTRIS-DC at CNR
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/20/services/862
Direct link	https://tools.actris-ares.eu/aviation-early-warning/
Contact	services@actris-ares.eu
Description	
<p>Early Warning for Aviation (EWA) is provided by the ACTRIS ARES Data Centre Unit for ACTRIS and EARLINET stations and consists of a volcanic ash and desert dust alert service aimed at mitigating risks related to aviation. The service provides colour-coded vertical maps of 3 alert levels and is intended to describe the concentration of volcanic ash or desert dust to conform to adopted hazardous aerosol concentration levels for aviation operations.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>The early warning product for volcanic ash and desert dust particles is of great interest to the aviation management authorities and the aviation industry. Besides this specific use, the service is of interest even for research purposes providing directly to the research community an indication of the presence of volcanic/dust particles and of their amount level.</p> <p>The methodology involves the identification of non-spherical particles (volcanic ash and desert dust) and the assignment to risk for aviation levels. The product has been developed in past projects using solely advanced lidar measurements and is available as a graphical interface.</p>	
Support to users	
<p>Ready-to-use web interface, support by email: services@actris-ares.eu https://tools.actris-ares.eu/aviation-early-warning/</p>	
Target user community	
<p>Research community, aviation management authorities and the aviation industry and users within research infrastructures</p>	

3.9.2 Number of visits

Figures 33 and 34 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2026-02-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 33. Early warning for aviation from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — Visits by month, 2026-02-09 – 2026-03-17.

Figure 34. Early warning for aviation from aerosol lidar ground-based observations — Visits by country, 2026-02-09 – 2026-03-17.

3.10 ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service

3.10.1 Description

Table 12 presents the main characteristics of the service, including its objectives, functionalities, user support, and target user community.

Table 12. Description of service ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service.

Service information	
Service name	ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service
Service ID	900
Installation	ICOS Carbon Portal at ULUND
IRISCC Catalogue of Services link	Onboarding still in progress
Direct link	https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/services/stilt-footprint
Contact	alex.vermeulen@icos-ri.eu ute.karstens@nateko.lu.se
Description	
<p>The ICOS STILT Footprint Service is an online tool for analysing the potential impact of natural and anthropogenic emissions on atmospheric concentrations of CO₂ and CH₄ at any location in Europe. The footprints are calculated on the basis of Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) analyses on a 1/8 x 1/12 grid for Europe and combined with surface maps of natural and anthropogenic tracer fluxes to simulate tracer concentrations at 3-hour intervals. Footprints, as well as CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations for ICOS and other existing or potential stations, can be viewed and downloaded for periods since 2006, or calculated on request for any location in Europe.</p>	
Scientific objectives and use	
<p>The scientific objective of the footprint tool is to provide estimates of which regions and surface emissions potentially influence greenhouse gas measurements at a given station; it is used to interpret concentration measurements and to design and evaluate atmospheric monitoring networks.</p>	
Support to users	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation on ICOS website: https://www.icos-cp.eu/data-services/services/stilt-footprint Support via footprint@icos-cp.eu and help@icos-cp.eu 	
Target user community	
<p>Scientific community and in particular PIs of atmospheric measurement stations.</p>	

3.10.2 Number of visits

Figures 35 and 36 provide an overview of the usage statistics of the service during the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31, including the temporal evolution of visits and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 35. ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service — Visits by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-25.

Figure 36. ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service — Visits by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-25.

3.10.3 Other metrics

Figures 37 and 38 present the usage metrics of the service over the period 2025-04-01 to 2026-03-31. A request corresponds to the number of model runs started by a user. The figures illustrate both the temporal evolution of these requests and their geographical distribution by country.

Figure 37. ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service — Metrics by month, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-25.

Figure 38. ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service — requests by country, 2025-04-01 – 2026-03-25.

4. Assessment report from IAP

An International Assessment Panel (IAP), established within WP8, is tasked with providing independent evaluations of the Virtual Access (VA) services at regular intervals of 18 months. For this initial phase, a 12-month milestone review allows to assess early implementation, to ensure the robustness of the evaluation process, and to allow timely adjustments before transitioning to the standard 18-month review cycle once the procedure is fully established.

Collaboration with WP8 enabled the extension of the PASS platform, originally developed for Transnational Access (TA), to support the evaluation of Virtual Access (VA) services by the IAP.

Each service was intended to be evaluated by two independent reviewers part of the IAP to ensure robustness and balance in the assessment process. Reviewers were provided with the information presented in Section 3 for each service, including the service description and the associated usage tracking data.

The evaluation was carried out using a structured assessment form (see Annex A.), ensuring consistency and comparability across services. The assessment considered key criteria such as scientific relevance, technical performance, usability, quality of documentation, and potential impact for the user community, **each scored on a scale from 0 to 5**.

It is important to signal that some of the invited reviewers did not submit their assessments within the reporting timeline. As a result, 12 reviewer submissions were received out of the 20 expected. Nevertheless, every R1 VA service received at least one independent assessment, ensuring that the evaluation exercise provides a meaningful and complete first coverage of the service portfolio.

In preparation for the next assessment cycle and the corresponding deliverable in 18 months, the review procedure will be revised in order to avoid similar limitations. Planned improvements include a more careful selection and confirmation process for reviewers, a longer review period (the present exercise allowed approximately three weeks), an increased number of reminders and follow-up actions, and the provision of administrative access to the relevant VA WP representatives within the PASS platform to improve monitoring and coordination of the review process.

Important notice: The assessment results presented below reflect a partial double-review coverage. While each VA service has been assessed by at least one independent reviewer, not all services received the two independent submissions originally planned. Readers should bear in mind that findings based on a single review may carry less robustness than

those supported by two independent evaluations. Results should therefore be interpreted accordingly, and no comparative conclusions should be drawn solely on the basis of the number of reviews received per service.

Table 13 provides a summary of the scores awarded by the IAP reviewers across all evaluated criteria. As noted in the disclaimer above, these scores reflect only the assessments that were successfully submitted within the reporting timeline and do not cover the full R1 VA service portfolio. The values presented represent averages computed over the available responses and should therefore be interpreted with caution, bearing in mind the incomplete coverage of this assessment cycle.

Table 13. Scores Summary for all services.

Number of reviews: 12 – Scores on a scale from 0 to 5	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	4.8
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	4.8
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	4.8
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	4.8
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	4.7
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	4.8
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	4.6
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	4
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	4.8

4.1 IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere

Table 14 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers' comments and responses.

Table 14. Scores Summary for service IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of ECVs in the Troposphere.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	5
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	4
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	4
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

It is highly relevant to enable users to see anomalies in atmospheric composition, especially for the upper atmosphere where data is relatively sparse.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

Although I do not have personal experience with the service, I see that the service has been in operation for some time and that a significant number of users visited.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

As I have no personal experience with the service I see from the use in the past that there is interest. I therefore assume that uptake is at least satisfactory.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

No

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

I believe that services like this are very valuable to the community at large. In the long run, I think that services like these could become a part of more generic virtual research environments (for atmospheric composition and climate change).

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- E-learning tutorials (with worked examples)
- Library of scientific use cases / showcase examples
- Written documentation / user manual

4.2 IAGOS Climatologies and Anomalies of VOCs

Table 15 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers' comments and responses.

Table 15. Scores Summary for service IAGOS anomalies of volatile organic compounds in the troposphere.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	4
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	4
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	5
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	4
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	4
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

This service gives access to very relevant information regarding the dispersion of plumes related to biomass burning. This is relevant to the community at large, including the satellite (earth observation) community.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

This service seems to be very easy to use, which makes it very attractive for the novice and experienced user.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

This service is highly relevant as it is. My suggestion would be to connect to more generic virtual research environments for atmospheric composition and climate change.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

No

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

See previous comment (regarding VRE).

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- E-learning tutorials (with worked examples)
- Library of scientific use cases / showcase examples
- Written documentation / user manual

4.3 IS-ENES Climate4Impact

Table 16 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers' comments and responses.

Table 16. Scores Summary for service CLIMATE4IMPACT portal.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	5
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	5
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	4
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

Variety of CMIP data provision in user-friendly way, but also in more advanced way for more detailed data provision. The ease-of-use makes it possible to provide data to a wider stakeholder group.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

Open and standardized user-friendly access to data. Proper user support is provided.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

The interface will likely work after this evaluation. Relatively large use of data, but not increase during the 1-year trial period.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

No

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

No other comments.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- Videos / screencasts
- Library of scientific use cases / showcase examples

4.4 IS-ENES Climate Model Data Access Portal

Table 17 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers' comments and responses.

Table 17. Scores Summary for service Climate Model Data Portal.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	4
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	4
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	5
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	3
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	4

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

These CMIP-data are of high relevance to a variety of climate model researchers and community-wide for further translation into stakeholder-driven user needs.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

Open data, and scope is wide and useful. Can be a bit of an obstacle to enter the portal for the first time and orient oneself on the services offered and instructions for use and download. Hence, there is a user barrier, but this is on the other hand unavoidable for such a wide range of data provided.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

There is no risk assessment provided on the change of data portal in the summer of 2026 in terms of user access friendliness. In addition: will the visibility of services be increased with the change of data portal? So far, the number of visits to the portal is limited, and not far-reaching. The visits are not increasing either on a 1-year horizon.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

No

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

This review is difficult due to lack of detailed information provided by the author in relation to each evaluation criteria. More work can be done to more clearly describe how criteria were dealt with.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- E-learning tutorials (with worked examples)
- Interactive webinars
- Library of scientific use cases / showcase examples

4.5 European Climate Assessment & Dataset

Table 18 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers' comments and responses.

Table 18. Scores Summary for service European Climate Assessment & Dataset.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	5
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	5
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	3
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

Very easy to access data in readable format for soil moisture and snow depth with a wide user base, from science users (aerosol research soil resuspension, climate, hydrology, forestry and agricultural research) and all the way to stakeholders (spatial planning, resources, adaptation, food security, ecosystem provision, and so on).

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

The ease-of-use makes it readily available to users, and the spatial coverage of data is unique.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

If also other infrastructures could provide data to this site, for example ICOS ecosystem stations, it would increase usage even more. The user statistics were not sufficiently presented in the review, so I could not see if the tendency is towards increasing visibility and data download or not.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

No

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

No other comments.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- Library of scientific use cases / showcase examples

4.6 ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol In-situ)

Table 19 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers’ comments and responses.

Table 19. Scores Summary for service RRT/NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements.

Number of reviews: 2	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	4
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	4.5
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	5
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	5
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	4.5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

The service is scientifically strong, well-positioned, and technically sound. It provides high-demand NRT data that can serve a wide range of purposes, from model evaluation and data assimilation to informing policy decisions. In terms of data coverage, it addresses important atmospheric variables, with a primary focus on aerosols, supported by the well-established ACTRIS/EBAS infrastructure. However, the information provided on its interdisciplinary potential is limited.

A very high value for users, including both inside and outside of the community. Interdisciplinarity potential is high.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

The service is strong in terms of usability and accessibility, offering open portals, EBAS NetCDF (NC) formats, visualisation tools, and helpdesk support. Its main added value lies in the timely delivery of NRT of (primarily) aerosol data, to be used in a wide range of applications. Possible limitations include common issues not specific to the service itself, such as data quality constraints linked to the preliminary nature of NRT data, as well as

technical barriers for non-expert users. Open Science and FAIR principles are well addressed.

Usability of the service is very high, very well documented and contributing to Open Science principles.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

Although the information in this section is not clearly provided within the proposal and subsequent navigation within the website, primarily in terms of the technical reliability of the services, it is evident that user activity in terms of visits per month and downloads of data ensures that the service will consider sustainable solutions to provide long-term availability of data.

Considering institutional support and long-term strategy the service has a sustainable future and potential for high impact.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

Not foreseen within open access scope, but neither can be totally excluded

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

Perhaps stronger advertising and especially training inside and outside of the community may be considered.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- Videos / screencasts
- Written documentation / user manual
- E-learning tutorials (with worked examples)
- Interactive webinars

4.7 ACTRIS RRT/NRT Quick Looks (Aerosol remote sensing)

Table 20 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers’ comments and responses.

Table 20. Scores Summary for service Aerosol Remote Sensing Quicklook Interface.

Number of reviews: 2	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	4
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	3.5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	4
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	4.5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	4
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	4.5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	4
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	4
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

The VA allows rapid visualization of the available lidar data, attenuated backscatter quicklooks and volume linear depolarization ratio. The service is valuable allowing a faster data interpretation and retrieval of atmospheric aerosol layering and variability. In this way the non-specialized scientist can quickly harvest the database.

The Quicklook interface will support the interpretation and understanding of atmospheric aerosol layering and variability.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

A nice feature is the availability of quicklooks from the data collected at other stations for the same data selected by the user. The VA is easy to use on the web interface.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

The user access is monitored and updates procedures are implemented (at the review moment a new version of the service is being prepared for release).

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

Not the case

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

User customizable quick look features will be highly valuable.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- Written documentation / user manual

4.8 ACTRIS ECV Climatologies

Table 21 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers' comments and responses.

Table 21. Scores Summary for service Climatologies and anomalies of selected ECVs from aerosol lidar ground-based observations.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	4
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	5
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	5
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	4
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

The Level 3 climatological data available through VA are valuable not only to the scientists in the atmospheric domain, but also to modelers, making available QC and harmonised data for an extended number of stations in Europe.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

The data are ready to use, from a web interface, making use of open science and FAIR rules. The data format is a standard one being easy to use, with level 3 data.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

The VA usage and user are monitored, the service seems to be scalable to the data volume and number of users. Not find info related to the maintenance of the service on a long term, outside projects.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

Not identified

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

The VA is highly valuable, being addressed to multiple users: atmospheric research community, users within research infrastructures and stakeholders, including modelers.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- Interactive webinars
- Written documentation / user manual

4.9 ACTRIS Volcanic Ash Alerts

Table 22 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers' comments and responses.

Table 22. Scores Summary for service Early warning for aviation from aerosol lidar ground-based observations.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	4
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	4
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	4
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	4
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	4
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	4

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

The service will provide a highly valuable outcome for aviation operations, but not only. The service results, namely volcanic ash and desert dust particles, can be also valuable for the scientific communities.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

The VA is feasible, the preliminary steps being done in previous projects, now being added the colour-coded vertical maps of 3 alert levels. The vertical information will be highly relevant to the aviation purpose and identification of ash and desert dust level altitude. No strict limitations are seen, solely the lidar data availability, which is not under DC control. The ready-to-use web interface assures the Open Science and FAIR principles.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

The operational readiness of the service is considered, starting from already implemented tools within the same areas. The service can be extended to multiple datasets and maintained on long-term after development with limited resources.

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

The plan involves the identification of non-spherical particles and the assignment to risk for aviation levels, the implementation schedules seems to be rather short.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- Written documentation / user manual

4.10 ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service

Table 23 presents the summary of evaluation scores for the service. The subsequent text provides the reviewers’ comments and responses.

Table 23. Scores Summary for service ICOS STILT Atmospheric footprint service.

Number of reviews: 1	
1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service	
1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements	5
1.2 Scientific and technical quality	5
1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance	5
2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation	
2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose	5
2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service	5
2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement	5
3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact	
3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability	5
3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support	5
Final Recommendation	
How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues?	5

Remarks

1 – Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

This is an excellent example of a service built on the vast efforts of data collection that make the data usable for scientific purposes.

2 – Suitability, Usability and Innovation

This service is scientifically relevant and technically well implemented. It is clear that long experience and well considered decisions have been taken along in the implementation.

3 – Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

The evidence provided shows a good use and uptake in the community.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly?

No

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Suggestions for improvement or additional considerations

Excellent work. Further connection to other services (related to i.e. air pollution) should be considered for further developments.

Training preferences

Which training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service?

- E-learning tutorials (with worked examples)
- Library of scientific use cases / showcase examples
- Written documentation / user manual

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Overall uptake of R1 VA services

The first year of operation of the R1 Virtual Access (VA) services confirms the successful deployment of a diverse portfolio of services through the IRISCC Catalogue of Services.

Over the reporting period (April 2025 – March 2026), the ten R1 services collectively recorded 9,437 visits, over 1.35 billion downloads, approximately 37.5 TB of data downloaded, and 420,669 requests, demonstrating significant aggregate uptake across the portfolio.

Usage statistics indicate a heterogeneous level of uptake across services. Well-established platforms such as climate data portals and modelling services show regular and sustained usage over the reporting period. In contrast, recently onboarded services or services with shorter observation windows exhibit more limited usage, reflecting their early stage of deployment. In several cases, usage statistics are incomplete or not yet available due to the ongoing implementation of monitoring systems.

These results highlight that the VA ecosystem is operational but still in a progressive adoption phase, with expected growth in usage over time.

5.2 Key findings from IAP assessment

The evaluation carried out by the International Assessment Panel (IAP) confirms the high scientific and technical quality of the services provided. The overall average scores are consistently high across most criteria, with values ranging from 4.0 to 4.8 out of 5.

Across the reviewed services, several strengths are consistently identified: strong alignment with IRISCC objectives and scientific priorities (avg. 4.8), high-quality data and robust scientific methodologies (avg. 4.8), good adherence to Open Science and FAIR principles (avg. 4.8), and clear potential for scientific and societal impact (avg. 4.8). The overall likelihood of recommending the services to colleagues reaches an average score of 4.8, reflecting a very positive reception from the panel.

The assessment also highlights strong performance in technical robustness and reliability (avg. 4.6), confirming that the services are well-implemented and operationally sound. User uptake and community engagement, while receiving the comparatively lowest average score (4.0), still reflects a satisfactory level of engagement for services at this early stage of deployment, and represents a natural area of growth as visibility and adoption increase over time. Reviewers across multiple services pointed to training resources – in particular e-learning tutorials, scientific use case libraries, and written documentation – as high-value additions that could further accelerate uptake.

Overall, these findings paint an encouraging picture: the RI VA services are scientifically excellent, technically reliable, and well-aligned with Open Science principles, providing a strong foundation on which to build broader community engagement in the next cycle.

5.3 Cross-analysis of usage and evaluation

The combined analysis of usage tracking and IAP assessments provides additional insights into the current state of the VA services.

Several encouraging patterns emerge. A number of services combine high IAP scores with substantial and sustained usage, confirming both their scientific excellence and their effective integration within existing research workflows. Other services received perfect IAP scores (5.0 across all criteria) alongside consistent user engagement, illustrating the strong potential of well-matured services to achieve both scientific recognition and broad community uptake.

Where usage appears more limited, this is generally explained by the recent onboarding of services rather than by any weakness in scientific quality, as confirmed by the uniformly high IAP scores across the portfolio. This decoupling between early-stage usage and scientific value is a natural feature of a first deployment cycle and is expected to resolve as services gain visibility over time.

While usage metrics are not yet fully harmonised or complete across all services, limiting the scope for a fully quantitative comparison, this cross-analysis nevertheless provides valuable insights into the relationship between scientific quality and user uptake. The results confirm that the RI VA portfolio is built on a solid scientific foundation, and underline the importance of continuing efforts to strengthen visibility and user engagement in future developments.

5.4 Key challenges

Based on the analysis of usage data and IAP feedback, a small number of cross-cutting challenges have been identified for the next cycle, alongside the many strengths already noted.

Monitoring and metrics remain incomplete for some services, with heterogeneity in tracking methodologies and definitions; completing this implementation is a priority for the next reporting period. User uptake and visibility, while satisfactory overall, still have room to grow for certain services, particularly outside established expert communities, and will benefit from the targeted outreach and training actions already identified by reviewers. Service maturity naturally varies across the portfolio, with recently onboarded services expected to reach higher usage levels as their deployment stabilises. Finally, usability and user support show some variability in documentation and guidance quality, which represents a concrete and actionable improvement opportunity for service providers.

An additional cross-cutting improvement area concerns the harmonisation and visibility of access, data usage, citation, and acknowledgement policies across the VA portfolio. While several services already provide clear guidance on data access conditions and attribution requirements, this information remains incomplete or inconsistently exposed across the full set of services. Strengthening these policies would improve transparency and ensure appropriate recognition of all partners contributing to the VA services and underlying datasets. In the longer term, the adoption of persistent identifiers such as DOIs for selected datasets and service outputs could further enhance traceability, reproducibility, and scientific reusability.

The IAP review process itself encountered some operational challenges during this first cycle. Reviewer response rates were lower than anticipated resulting in single-reviewer coverage for several services rather than the intended double-review. While this is a limitation to acknowledge, it is also a valuable lesson: the review procedure has been thoroughly analysed and a set of concrete improvements has already been identified and will be implemented ahead of the next assessment cycle, as detailed in Section 4.

5.5 Recommendations

In light of these findings, several recommendations are proposed for the next cycle.

Usage tracking should be strengthened by completing the implementation of the VA monitoring system and harmonising usage indicators across services, with particular attention to services that were not yet able to report metrics during this first period. Visibility and outreach could be improved through targeted communication strategies and training

activities – in line with the preferences expressed by IAP reviewers, priority should be given to e-learning tutorials with worked examples, libraries of scientific use cases, and written documentation. Usability and user support should be enhanced by standardising documentation and developing the training materials identified above.

Service providers should be supported in improving technical robustness and ensuring long-term sustainability beyond the project duration, a point raised by several reviewers. IAP feedback should be systematically transmitted to service providers and its integration into service development monitored over time.

Finally, the IAP review process should be strengthened for the next assessment cycle, as outlined in Section 4, to ensure full double-review coverage and a more robust and representative evaluation of the RI VA service portfolio. This could include a more rigorous reviewer selection and confirmation process, an extended review timeline, and the provision of administrative access to VA WP representatives within the PASS platform to improve coordination and monitoring of the review exercise.

5.6 Outlook

The RI phase represents a key milestone in the implementation of Virtual Access within IRISCC. The results of this first reporting period are encouraging: the ten RI services are operational, scientifically excellent, and already serving a broad international user community across Europe and beyond, as evidenced by the usage data and the uniformly high IAP scores recorded across all evaluation criteria.

Future releases will build on this strong foundation by improving the visibility and usability of existing services, expanding the portfolio of available services, and strengthening the overall impact of Virtual Access within the climate risk research community. The lessons learned from this first assessment cycle – both on the service side and on the review process itself – provide a clear roadmap for continuous improvement, and position the IRISCC VA ecosystem for broader adoption and greater scientific impact in the cycles ahead.

6. References

References	
No	Description/Link
r1	IRISCC Deliverable D8.2 Optimised IRISCC VA Management System. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15592864
r2	IRISCC Deliverable D9.1 Report defining and describing R1 services. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15774382

7. Annex

A. VA Review form

Completed - Apr 17 2026

Review Form – Virtual Access (VA) Services

VA Merit Review Form

Thank you for agreeing to contribute your expert opinion to the evaluation of this Virtual Access (VA) service.

The evaluation is a key phase of the IRISCC process, aimed at assessing the scientific and technical quality, relevance, and usability of the VA service, as well as its value for the research community.

Virtual Access (VA) in IRISCC provides researchers with remote, online access to datasets, data analysis tools, modelling services, and scientific resources offered by the IRISCC research infrastructure network, free of charge for eligible users.

Each VA service is evaluated by an ad-hoc panel composed of up to two members of the IRISCC International Assessment Panel (IAP), selected based on their expertise in the relevant scientific or technical domain.

The evaluation consists of:

- Reviewing the service description and available documentation
- Assessing the scientific relevance and potential impact of the service
- Evaluating usability, accessibility, and level of user support
- Considering available usage indicators (if applicable)
- Assigning scores for each evaluation criterion
- Providing brief comments to support the scores

No sensitive data is collected. All gathered information will be used only for the VA evaluation process. All information and responses to this questionnaire will be restricted to participants involved in the evaluation. The individual responses and consent forms will be stored at CNR, Italy, for the duration of the project, until 30 September 2028.

For more information, please refer to our privacy notices: https://imaa.cnr.it/?page_id=2889, <https://www.luke.fi/en/documents/iriscc-privacy-notice>.

By submitting the form, you acknowledge that you have read and understood the above information.

VA Service Identification

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VA Service name

RRT/NRT visualization for aerosol in-situ measurements

VA service provider

ACTRIS-DC_NILU

VA service related RI(s)

ACTRIS

VA service direct link

<https://ebas-nrt.nilu.no/>

Note to Reviewers

VA services covered by this evaluation span a wide range of types — datasets, analysis tools, modelling services, and scientific resources — with significantly different levels of maturity, scope, and user interaction models. As a result, not all evaluation criteria may be equally applicable to every service. Reviewers are invited to mark criteria as "Not Applicable" where relevant, and to use the comments field to briefly justify this assessment.

For the purposes of the assessment, reviewers may access the service at the provided URL and test its functionality directly.

Evaluation Criteria – Section 1: Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

This section evaluates the scientific and technical value of the VirtualAccess (VA) service itself. In the context of IRISCC VirtualAccess, the assessment focuses on the quality, relevance, and potential impact of the service provided to the research community.

Please assign a score for each criterion using whole numbers from 0 to 5.

1.1 Alignment with IRISCC strategic priorities/call requirements

Please consider and rate:

- The relevance of the VA service to IRISCC objectives, particularly in addressing climate change risks
- The extent to which the service enables or supports multi-, inter-, or transdisciplinary research
- The contribution of the service to the integration of data, tools, or knowledge across scientific domains

5 (Excellent)

1.2 Scientific and technical quality

Please consider and rate:

- The clarity and relevance of the scientific scope of the service
- The soundness of the underlying scientific methodologies and theoretical foundations
- The quality and reliability of the data, models, or tools provided (e.g. validation, benchmarking, uncertainty quantification)
- The level of scientific documentation and transparency (e.g. peer-reviewed references, technical reports, change logs)

5 (Excellent)

1.3 Scientific Impact and Community Relevance

Please consider and rate:

- The potential of the service to support high-quality research and generate new knowledge
- The relevance and usefulness of the service for the broader scientific community, including interdisciplinary potential
- The likelihood of the service being cited, referenced, or built upon in subsequent research

4 (Very good)

Comments – Section 1: Scientific and Technical Value of the VA Service

Please provide a brief justification for the scores assigned in this section, with particular attention to:

- Scientific relevance and positioning within the domain
- Interdisciplinary potential

Please highlight the main reasons for the marks given.

The service is scientifically strong, well-positioned, and technically sound. It provides high-demand NRT data that can serve a wide range of purposes, from model evaluation and data assimilation to informing policy decisions. In terms of data coverage, it addresses important atmospheric variables, with a primary focus on aerosols, supported by the well-established ACTRIS/EBAS infrastructure. However, the information provided on its interdisciplinary potential is limited.

Evaluation Criteria - Section 2: Suitability, Usability and Innovation of the VA Service

This section evaluates the suitability of the Virtual Access (VA) service for its intended user community, as well as its usability and level of innovation.

The focus is on how effectively the service meets user needs, facilitates access and use, and provides added value through innovative features.

Please assign a score for each criterion using whole numbers from 0 to 5.

2.1 Suitability for User Needs and Fitness-for-Purpose

Please consider and rate:

- The extent to which the VA service provides relevant functionalities, datasets, or tools aligned with the needs of its target user community
- The clarity of the service scope, intended applications, and limitations
- The degree to which the service is fit-for-purpose for typical scientific or technical use cases
- The added value of the service compared to existing alternatives (if applicable)

5 (Excellent)

2.2 Usability and Innovation of the VA Service

Please consider and rate:

- Ease of access and use (e.g. authentication procedures, interfaces, workflows)
- Quality, completeness, and clarity of documentation and user guidance
- Availability and effectiveness of user support (e.g. helpdesk, tutorials, examples)
- Innovative aspects of the service, in terms of:
 1. Functionalities or technologies
 2. Advanced data integration or processing capabilities
 3. Interactive, scalable, or user-driven features

4 (very good)

2.3 Open Science and FAIR Enablement

Please consider and rate:

Scientific relevance and potential

- The potential of the VA service to contribute to Open Science practices and data sharing within the research community
- The potential for reuse, interoperability, and integration in other research workflows

Implementation level

- The extent to which the VA service implements FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) in practice
- Availability and quality of metadata, standards, and interoperability mechanisms
- Accessibility conditions (e.g. open access, authentication requirements, licensing)
- Support for data reuse and reproducibility (e.g. standard formats, APIs, versioning, traceability)

5 (Excellent)

Comments – Section 2: Suitability, Usability and Innovation

Please provide a brief justification for the scores assigned in this section, highlighting:

- Strengths and weaknesses in terms of usability and accessibility
- The level of innovation and added value of the service
- Any limitations or barriers affecting the effective use of the service
- The degree to which Open Science and FAIR principles are effectively implemented

Please highlight the main reasons for the marks given.

The service is strong in terms of usability and accessibility, offering open portals, EBAS NetCDF (NC) formats, visualisation tools, and helpdesk support. Its main added value lies in the timely delivery of NRT of (primarily) aerosol data, to be used in a wide range of applications. Possible limitations include common issues not specific to the service itself, such as data quality constraints linked to the preliminary nature of NRT data, as well as technical barriers for non-expert users. Open Science and FAIR principles are well addressed.

Evaluation Criteria - Section 3: Service Implementation, Performance and Impact

This section evaluates the quality, effectiveness, and maturity of the Virtual Access (VA) service implementation. The focus is on the operational performance of the service, its uptake by the user community, and its sustainability.

Please assign a score for each criterion using whole numbers from 0 to 5.

3.1 Technical Robustness and Reliability

Please consider and rate:

- The technical stability and availability of the service (e.g. uptime, performance, error handling)
- The maturity and operational readiness of the service infrastructure
- The clarity and organisation of access points, interfaces, and delivery workflows
- The existence of monitoring, maintenance, and update procedures

0 (Not Applicable)

3.2 User Uptake, Community Engagement and Support

For new VA Services developed in the IRISCC project, please consider and rate:

- The sustainability of the VA service beyond the project duration (e.g. institutional support, funding, long-term hosting)
- The scalability of the service in terms of data volume, number of users, or computational demand
- The level of technical and organisational readiness to ensure continuity of access
- The alignment with best practices for long-term data and service preservation

0 (Not Applicable)

Comments – Section 3: Implementation, Performance and Impact

Please provide a brief justification for the scores assigned in this section, highlighting:

- Strengths and weaknesses of the service implementation and reliability
- Evidence of user uptake and community engagement
- Risks or limitations related to sustainability and long-term availability

Please highlight the main reasons for the marks given.

Although the information in this section is not clearly provided within the proposal and subsequent navigation within the website, primarily in terms of the technical reliability of the services, it is evident that user activity in terms of visits per month and downloads of data ensures that the service will consider sustainable solutions to provide long-term availability of data.

Ethics

Are there any possible ethical issues that are not addressed convincingly? (e.g., data privacy, intellectual property, dual-use concerns, data sharing restrictions, AI use)

None

Feedback to VA Service Providers

Please provide feedback on the scientific goals, work plan, and other aspects of the VA service. Are there specific strengths or weaknesses you would like to highlight, and do you have any suggestions for improvement or additional considerations? Your feedback will be transmitted to the Service providers.

-

Training and Capacity Building

Based on the VA service, which of the following training resources do you think would help the user group to make the best use of the VA service? (Check all that apply)

Responses Selected:

- Videos / screencasts
- Written documentation / user manual

Final Recommendation

How likely are you to recommend the VA service to colleagues? (1 = Definitely not, 5 = Certainly)

4

Your reviewer dashboard does not store completed reviews. If you'd like a copy, please download and save your review before submitting.